

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND NATURAL LANGUAGE PROCESSING FOR EASY-TO-READ TEXTS

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Abstract

Access to information is a fundamental human right that contributes to freedom of expression and self-determination. However, information availability alone is not enough: the way in which information is expressed and presented on paper or in digital format can be extremely complicated to understand and act upon for a highly diverse set of people with varying ranges of reading, writing and understanding abilities. For a long time, artificial intelligence (AI) and natural language processing (NLP) have dedicated research efforts in the field of automatic text simplification to the development of methods to automate the production of easy-to-read texts. However, in spite of AI hype, the problem persists. Current NLP models such as large language models (LLMs) are still not well understood, and their use in the development of text simplification needs careful assessment. In this paper, having identified the need for easy-to-read, accessible texts, we provide a light overview of current methods in NLP and provide a lay explanation of several techniques applied to lexically and syntactically modified texts to make them simpler to read and understand. We conclude by raising awareness on the use of general tools to address this very challenging problem that can affect contemporary lives.

Keywords: easy-to-read; text simplification; natural language processing; lexical simplification; syntactic simplification.

LA INTEL·LIGÈNCIA ARTIFICIAL I EL PROCESSAMENT DEL LLENGUATGE NATURAL PER A TEXTOS DE LECTURA FÀCIL

Resum

L'accés a la informació és un dret humà fonamental que contribueix a la llibertat d'expressió i l'autodeterminació. Això no obstant, la mera disponibilitat de la informació no és suficient, atès que la manera en què s'expressa i es presenta en paper o en format digital pot ser extremadament complicada d'entendre i de processar per a una població molt diversa, amb habilitats de lectura, escriptura i comprensió d'allò més dispars. Durant molt de temps, la intel·ligència artificial (IA) i el processament del llenguatge natural (PLN) han dedicat esforços de recerca al camp de la simplificació automàtica de textos amb l'objectiu de desenvolupar mètodes per automatitzar la producció de textos de lectura fàcil. Tot i així, malgrat l'expectació generada al voltant de la IA, el problema persisteix. Els models actuals de PLN, com ara els models de llenguatge extens (LLM), encara no estan desenvolupats del tot, i el seu ús en la simplificació de textos requereix una supervisió minuciosa. En aquest article, després d'haver identificat la necessitat de disposar de textos accessibles i de lectura fàcil, proporcionem una visió de conjunt dels mètodes actuals en PLN i presentem una explicació senzilla de diverses tècniques que s'apliquen a textos modificats lèxicament i sintàcticament per fer-los més fàcils de llegir i d'entendre. Concloem destacant la importància d'utilitzar eines generals per tractar aquest problema tan complex que afecta la realitat contemporània.

Paraules clau: lectura fàcil; simplificació de textos; processament del llenguatge natural; simplificació lèxica; simplificació sintàctica.

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1 Introduction

In order to make informed decisions and actively participate in society, people need to be able to understand written information, not only up-to-date information such as news and entertainment but, more importantly, information that affects their daily lives, such as that related to their health (e.g., patient information leaflets provided with medicines, medical procedures and possible consequences of treatments), their finances (e.g., banking information, mortgages and inflation rates), and their lives as citizens of democratic societies (e.g., rights and obligations and participatory processes). All these needs impose obligations on the health system, the judiciary and other democratic institutions (e.g., city councils, central government and transnational political bodies) to provide much-needed content to citizens.

Access to information is a human right (see Article 19 of the [Universal Declaration of Human Rights](#)) and, according to the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), the [Right to Information](#) is fundamental and key to building an inclusive knowledge society: “access to information serves as an integral part of freedom of expression and is an important tool for promoting the rule of law, other rights and building trust.”

But availability of information *per se* is not enough, since the way in which information is transmitted – in text, speech or other contemporary forms of communication that go beyond textual forms – can be very difficult for people in several sectors of society to understand. Those who find it difficult to derive meaning from content (text or otherwise) are a diverse group of individuals with varying ranges of reading, writing and understanding abilities. This part of the population includes, for instance, those with low levels of literacy, intellectual disabilities, dyslexia, aphasia, temporary impairments, limited language skills (e.g., second-language learners, immigrants, and displaced populations), or the deaf. Older people¹ – a demographic which will constitute 30 per cent of the population of Europe by 2050 and which, according to some estimates, will reach 2 billion worldwide by 2025 – may fall into this category, as they can be affected by significant cognitive, physical or sensorial decline as they age (Murman, 2015; Arch, 2009; Beard et al., 2016) however there are some gaps in our knowledge and much integration and adoption still required. The Web Accessibility Initiative: Ageing Education and Harmonisation (WAI-AGE). Also worthy of note are the results of an Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) adult literacy report (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, 2013) involving 16–65 year olds in 24 countries, which revealed that, on average, as much as 16.7% of the population only understands “basic vocabulary”, and approximately 50% understands only basic syntactic constructions. Non-native speakers and people with various reading or intellectual impairments also have problems understanding lexically and syntactically complex sentences.

According to the UNESCO Institute for Statistics, a total of 750 million adults are either illiterate or have low literacy levels (UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2017). Among these are *persons with disabilities*, who account for 15% of the world’s population and have been identified as being at greater risk of illiteracy (UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2018). According to the [Special Olympics](#), *persons with intellectual disabilities* represent 1 to 3% of the world’s population (75 to 225 million people). Moreover, in the fourth quarter of 2018 alone, migrants accounted for 144,166 arrivals of non-EU citizens to Europe (International Organization for Migration, 2019): this group will be at a disadvantage when they have to access information in a language they have yet to master.

Also relevant in this context is the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities ([CRPD](#)), which includes accessibility as a key enabler of a more inclusive society. Accessibility is the ability of any product, service, content or environment to be used by people with the widest range of

1 People over 65 years old.

abilities (including linguistic and cognitive abilities). The CRPD also considers accessibility as an enabler of democratic participation rights such as freedom of expression and self-determination. Consequently, a lack of accessibility can be linked to a risk of exclusion for persons unable to participate equally due to linguistic barriers.

The question is how to make information more accessible for those who need it. Since the late nineties, many organisations have raised awareness about fundamental information being written in a way that is too difficult to understand for many people. Initiatives to palliate this deficit include *plain language* and *easy-to-read*, two different methods whose overall objective is to make information more accessible.

Under these initiatives, guidelines for how to write more accessible texts were proposed, but applying these to produce accessible material is heavily dependent on highly-trained human editors, considerably limiting the production potential of easy-to-read or plain language texts. Moreover, while websites offering accessible information exist in several languages – for example, [Planeta Fácil](#), the news portal offered in Spanish by Plena Inclusión Madrid; the news portal [8 Sidor](#) in Swedish; or UK charity United Response's easy-to-read news in English – they can only publish a fraction of mainstream content in easy language. In spite of these good initiatives, it is evident that, without technological support, the production of accessible texts at a reasonable pace will not be achievable.

As for plain language, we have identified a number of initiatives, including Plain Language Association International ([PLAIN](#)), which promotes clear communication in any language; the [Plain English Campaign](#) in the United Kingdom; and initiatives in Latin America (Arenas Arias, 2023) such as the Clear Language Strategy in Colombia, or the Clear Language Observatory in Argentina to promote the use of plain language for all citizens in contexts such as the judiciary.

In this article, having discussed accessible information concepts, we will briefly introduce concepts related to the relevant AI field of natural language processing, then provide a light overview of methods and approaches to the automatic production of easy-to-read texts. We will also draw attention to initiatives within the judicial, scientific and democratic sectors that aim to make information more accessible for all.

2 Accessibility, clear communication and easy-to-read

Before being considered a research topic, two methods of producing accessible communication thrived on the involvement of end-users, user associations, family members, support persons or national administrations concerned about lack of accessibility in documents. These methods are *easy-to-read* and *plain language*. Both provide guidelines including layout and linguistic recommendations that aim to improve the readability of content, whether printed or digital, written or oral (Matamala, 2022).

One main difference between plain language and easy-to-read is that the latter focuses on a greater degree of linguistic and layout simplification and is rule-based (Bott & Saggion, 2011; Nomura et al., 2010; Saggion et al., 2015). The International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA) defines easy-to-read as follows:

easy-to-read [...] means a linguistic adaptation of a text that makes both reading and comprehension easier. The aim of easy-to-read publications is to present clear and easily understood texts appropriate for different age groups. To achieve such a product, the writer/publisher must take into consideration content, language, illustrations, as well as graphic layout. (Nomura et al., 2010)

Whereas, according to PLAIN, a communication is in plain language “if its wording, structure, and design are so clear that the intended audience can easily find what they need, understand what they find, and use that information”.

But there are several other differences between the two methods. One of the most evident is that easy-to-read relies heavily on linguistic adaptation, while plain language includes it. Additionally, easy-to-read is strongly associated with people with disabilities, while plain language is not. From a sociolinguistic viewpoint, this difference may contribute to stigmatisation in the case of easy-to-read, while the same does not apply in the case of plain language (Maaß, 2020). From a methodology perspective, easy-to-read is a user-centred method which includes and involves the end-user in the process of creation and validation of the comprehensibility of the final text or communication artefact (Gallardo et al., 2018). This validation is sometimes carried out in groups with the assistance of a facilitator who moderates the group validation (International Organization for Standardization, 2023; Maaß, 2020; Asociación Española de Normalización, 2018).

Over the years, several other proposals and guidelines have suggested ways of producing writing that is clear for all. Basic English (Ogden, 1932), a reduced vocabulary language of just a few hundred word forms and a restricted number of grammatical rules, was conceived as a tool for international communication or a kind of interlingua. While plain language (Brown, 1995) is an Anglo-Saxon initiative, the French language variety Rational French (Barthe et al., 1999) was proposed to improve text readability and facilitate comprehension in a highly technical domain, as well as, more recently, the French [FALC](#) (“*facile à lire et à comprendre*”) and Spanish *lectura fácil* (García, 2012), a movement adopted by several organisations including [Plena Inclusión](#), [Asociació Lectura Fàcil](#) and [Discapnet](#).

Interest in implementing easy-to-read at European level is evidenced by projects funded by the European Commission, such as [Able to Include](#), Easy Access for Social Inclusion Training (EASIT), [Easy reading](#) and [Train2Validate](#).

At national levels, joint and individual efforts from academia and end-user associations are also yielding data and output, although the development of easy-to-read is different in each country. Germany has made considerable advances in guidelines for easy-to-read, as has Spain, whereas in countries such as Italy, the guidelines have merely been revised, and in others, such as Romania, no guidelines yet exist.

The following rules taken from Šveřepa (2021), available for 18 languages, suggest ways to write more readable and understandable texts:

At the sentence level:

- Keep sentences short
- Use active voice instead of passive voice
- Use positive instead of negative sentences

At the word level:

- Use words people will know well
- Do not use difficult words
- Use the same word to describe the same thing

Maaß (2020) found that, of the 120 rules established by three different easy-to-read methods, only seventeen rules were common to all three. Among the common rules are specifications for layout (e.g.,

text is left aligned), word structure (e.g., short words, no abbreviations), vocabulary (e.g., explain words if needed), sentence structure (e.g., short sentences), semantics (e.g., no negation) and text (e.g., no lexical variation, reader addressed directly).

It is evident that, no matter the guidelines, rules are highly subjective and therefore open to interpretation. For example, what does it mean to use a word that people will understand? This requirement needs a lexical model for the intended readership. Equally, what is meant by “keep sentences short”? What would be a reasonable cut-off length, based on what empirical research? Moreover, it would be rather awkward to avoid using the negative verb form in certain situations. For example, how could the expression, “*In case of emergency, do not use the elevator*” be rendered to avoid the use of the negative? Certainly, “*Use the emergency exit*” is a sentence in the affirmative, but it does not specifically restrict use of the elevator. The reality is that empirical research in easy-to-read is considerably scarce (González-Sordé & Matamala, 2024; Nomura et al., 2010) compared to other related fields such as linguistics, computational linguistics, translation or special needs education. Although the topic has gained greater scholarly attention in recent years, sometimes research reports have produced apparently contradictory findings (Fajardo et al., 2014) the framework provided by Kintsch’s Construction-Integration Model (1988 between guidelines and actual text understanding by target easy-to-read populations.

3 Natural language processing (NLP)

Natural language processing (Manning & Schütze, 2000) is a field within the realm of artificial intelligence (Russell & Norvig, 2010) whose overall objective is to study, implement and evaluate methods which will give computer systems the ability to understand (Allen, 1995) and generate human language (Reiter & Dale, 2006). Given the complexity of human language, it is somehow implied that computer programs will need to be equipped with, or at least leverage, theories of the lexicon, grammar, discourse and pragmatics of language (Crystal, 1987) to achieve language understanding and production as humans do, although many current NLP proposals seem to dismiss this claim (Collobert et al., 2011). The NLP field has addressed several sub-areas of research of considerable complexity (in the sense of requiring “language understanding”), including automatic text summarisation, question answering, dialogue, information extraction, text classification and language inference. Generally speaking, to support any intelligent language processing activity, sentences will need to be analysed by a number of components (other problems and techniques in NLP can be found in Mitkov [2021]), such as recognising named entities, parsing sentences with respect to the grammar of the language, and producing a semantic representation of the sentence, including disambiguation, for its use in different concrete applications. At the text level, automated discourse analysis processes that identify relations between sentences and coreference resolution to link related entities or events mentioned in a text are also relevant. These processes have evolved from rule-based systems (regular expressions, context-free grammars, dependency-grammars, etc.) or systems based on lexical knowledge bases or taxonomies, such as WordNets (Miller et al., 1990) or BabelNet (Navigli & Ponzetto, 2010), to machine learning approaches that rely on the availability of human-annotated corpora (e.g., treebanks, human abstracts, annotated dialogues and human categorised documents) to automatically induce statistical taggers, parsers, named entity recognisers and classifiers. High-quality annotated and ethically controlled datasets are vitally important in the training of algorithms, but creating human annotated datasets is extremely difficult and time consuming.

If the development of the World Wide Web made electronic texts widely available to large sectors of the world’s population, effectively democratising information access to text and media, in recent years we have witnessed the way these resources have contributed to a paradigmatic change in the NLP field: a data-driven paradigm which does not rely on linguistic theories or rules, but rather “learns” – from the available data

found in massive amounts of text – how to model knowledge about text and words in context (Collobert et al., 2011; Devlin et al., 2019; Mikolov et al., 2013; Raffel et al., 2020; Vaswani et al., 2017). Computers can leverage this data in self-supervised fashion to effectively model human language by analysing words in context. This, together with the development of [powerful machine learning architectures](#) and [fast processing units](#) for training, contributed to the development of large language models (LLMs), massive neural networks (with billions of connexions) able to predict, given a sequence of words, the next word in the sequence (e.g., generate text), or suggest word replacements for a given word in the content. Since the launch of ChatGPT by OpenAI in 2023, several technological companies have released a variety of LLMs such as Gemini Ultra (Google), GPT-4 (OpenAI), Claude 2 (Anthropic), Inflection-2 (Inflection AI), and Llama 2 (Meta), to name a few, all of which are currently being used in different application contexts with remarkable success.

4 Text simplification and natural language processing

Given the urgent need to produce texts in plain or easy-to-read language, the question is to determine the nature of the contribution artificial intelligence and natural language processing can make in this context. The availability of an automated tool that can assist text production during the whole adaptation process or in some of the production stages of writing or translating into easy-to-read would be of utmost relevance for several communities.

Automatic text simplification is a technology which, over twenty years ago, started to adapt the content of a text to the specific needs of a target population, making the text more readable and understandable for them (Saggion, 2017). It can therefore be seen as a way to automate the translation or transformation of original texts into easy-to-read versions. Given this social relevance, there is considerable interest in this research field, and a sequence of events related to it has been taking place at major NLP conferences.² Since sentence complexity and lexical complexity are two very important questions to address in order to make information more understandable (both plain language and easy-to-read indicate sentence length and vocabulary adaptation), scholars have considered, among others, two main axes of research:

Lexical simplification (Paetzold & Specia, 2017) aims to find complex words, and simpler substitutes to replace them. These two sub-tasks are usually referred to as complex word identification (Zampieri et al., 2017) and substitute generation. But for a full autonomous lexical simplification system, there is also the need to somehow rank the found substitutes so as to identify the simpler or most appropriate one and appropriately use it to replace the complex word. While identifying complex words can be thought of as a binary classification task (whether complex or otherwise), recent research considers word simplicity (or complexity) in a continuum and proposes lexical complexity prediction, which aims to classify word complexity according to a scale (North et al., 2023). *Syntactic simplification* (Aranzabe et al., 2012; Bott & Saggion, 2011; Chandrasekar et al., 1996; Woodsend & Lapata, 2011) studies and develops methods to simplify sentences by transforming them into simpler equivalents. For example, relative or subordinate clauses or passive constructions – which may be very difficult to read – could be transformed into simpler sentences or into the active form.

More often than not, the target user of the simplification system has not been considered and the development of models is based on (i) general ideas about what it means for a text to be simple (e.g. easy-to-read guidelines), or (ii) the product of simplification datasets. In spite of this deficit, it is worth mentioning that several works have indeed paid attention to the target population during the design or

² The Third Workshop on Text Simplification, Accessibility and Readability ([TSAR](#)), or the 3rd Workshop on Tools and Resources for REAding Difficulties ([READI](#)).

the evaluation phase of the research. A number of studies have illustrated how dyslexic readers (Rello et al., 2013), people with intellectual disabilities (Saggion et al., 2015), the visually impaired (Sauvan et al., 2020) or the deaf (Alonzo et al., 2020) have been taken into consideration.

Lexical and sentence simplification, however, neglect an important aspect related to the further adaptation of a whole text. Such adaptation will need methods for ordering and connecting sentences with easy-to-read connectors; methods to correctly generate referring expressions to designate discourse elements introduced in the text; investigation into techniques to enrich the text with appropriate descriptions, definitions, or explanations; and methods to remove unnecessary or too detailed information.

We have previously mentioned rule-based systems in NLP, which have been applied in sentence simplification, for example, to identify sentences containing syntactic phenomena which are a barrier to readability or comprehension. Such phenomena include, for example, the presence of appositions, relative or other types of subordinate and coordinate clauses, and sentences in passive voice. Once identified in actual sentences, a re-writing operation may be applied to produce simpler sentences (e.g., creating a new sentence with the relative clause and a sentence with the main clause). Rule-based identification and transformation requires the encoding of linguistic knowledge, which is usually done by expert linguists.

When parallel data is available (see next section), text simplification can be thought of as a machine translation problem (translating from a complex language into a simple one). And in this line, several methods have been tried, such as the use of statistical machine translation (Specia, 2010; Stajner & Saggion, 2015; Wubben et al., 2012) or, more recently, neural machine translation (Nisioi et al., 2017). Since the release of the Transformer architecture in NLP (Vaswani et al., 2017), with its variations (encoders, decoders and encoder-decoders) and sequence to sequence models, research on text simplification has changed considerably. For example, there has recently been increased interest in conditional training of sequence-to-sequence models (e.g., embedding control tokens during training), applied to control summarisation output, for example, or to control the style of the generated text (e.g., for politeness). In text simplification, this method was used to control the “grade level” of the simplified text, its length or its syntactic complexity, achieving very promising results (Scarton & Specia, 2018). Recent research has shown that adding specific information to condition the type of output, via “trainable” control tokens (Martin et al., 2020), does help improve the performance of sentence simplification models quite significantly, with several works achieving state of the art in English and Spanish (Sheang & Saggion, 2021; Stajner et al., 2022) using LLMs such as the encoder-decoder T5 (Raffel et al., 2020) or BART (Lewis et al., 2020) and their variations.

Concerning lexical simplification, several past approaches used traditional count-based word vectors and available dictionaries for modelling word semantics and to select simple word replacement for complex words (Biran et al., 2011; Bott et al., 2012). These traditional vector models have recently been replaced in simplification approaches by word embedding, learned from huge text collections (Glavaš & Štajner, 2015). Nowadays, large-scale language models such as BERT and its variations have been applied to predict substitution candidates for complex words. For example, LS-BERT (Qiang et al., 2020) which will inevitably produce a large number of spurious candidates. We present a simple LS approach that makes use of the Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT uses the masked language model (MLM) of BERT to predict a set of candidate substitution words and their associated probability. In this context, the MLM predicts substitute words which are ranked for simplicity using probabilities, a language model, a paraphrase database, word frequency, and word semantic similarity with the target word. Very recent work presented at TSAR 2022 (Saggion et al., 2022) and MLSP 2024 (Shardlow et al., 2024) evaluation frameworks have demonstrated that LLMs are in fact the best performance models for lexical simplification, with techniques such as “prompting” being used to condition the LLMs to produce a simplification or suggest alternative words. Note, however, that these models underperform when simplifying low-resourced languages.

4.1 Data for text simplification

Empirical research on text simplification has relied on the availability of simplification datasets. Generally speaking, datasets for sentence simplification consist of parallel pairs of sentences (i.e., a complex sentence and its simplification). Several datasets have been collected in order to train or evaluate the performance text simplification systems, most of them for English. For sentence simplification, Wiki-Large (Zhang & Lapata, 2017) is the largest and most commonly used dataset for training English sentence simplification. It contains 296,402 sentence pairs from automatically-aligned complex-simple sentence pairs from document-aligned English Wikipedia and Simple English Wikipedia articles. Other datasets such as MTurk (Horn et al., 2014) and ASSET (Alva-Manchego et al., 2020), also in English, are used for evaluation. Both datasets contain 2,000 samples for validation and 359 samples for testing. Newsela (Xu et al., 2015) is a high-quality dataset in English and Spanish with human simplifications of different readability levels. Datasets for other languages also exist, such as Simplext for Spanish, PorSimples for Brazilian Portuguese (Gasperin et al., 2009), and SIMPITIKI (Tonelli et al., 2016) and [PaCCSS-IT](#) for Italian. In comparison to English, datasets for other languages are smaller. For example, the FIRST dataset (Mitkov & Štajner, 2014) contains just 25 documents in three languages, while a dataset for the Basque language (Gonzalez-Dios et al., 2018) contains a little over 200 sentences. However, available datasets are not without their problems: some have been mined from the Web (for example, Wikipedia and Simple Wikipedia) by automatic means and without quality control and diversity. Moreover, the target audience of the simplification is unclear. Datasets which follow clear standards for their creation are the Simplext Corpus, PortSimples Corpus and the Newsela Corpus, among others.

4.2 Datasets for lexical simplification

Where resources for lexical simplification are of concern, datasets are sets of sentences where a target word or expression has been identified as complex and a set of substitutes has been proposed by human informants. Availability of data for development or fine-tuning of models to effectively handle text simplification is a pre-requisite. Data is needed to train models or fine-tune or prompt engineer tasks, as well as to evaluate and benchmark them. As is the case for many other NLP tasks, the most work carried out to date has been for English – SemEval-2012 (Specia et al., 2012), LSEVAL (De Belder & Moens, 2012), LexMTurk (Horn et al., 2014), [BENCHLS](#), [NONSEVAL](#) and CEFR-LS – while relatively little has been carried out for other languages: for example, EASIER (Alarcón et al., 2024) and ALEXSIS (Ferrés & Saggion, 2022) for Spanish, FrenLys (Hmida et al., 2018) for French, HanLS (Qiang et al., 2021) for Chinese, and SNOW E4 (Kajiwara & Yamamoto, 2015) for Japanese. One recent development has seen an increase in resources for lexical complexity prediction and lexical simplification, with the release of the MLSP 2024 dataset, comprising around 6,000 instances of lexical complexity prediction and lexical simplification on common contexts across 10 languages (Shardlow, 2024a; Shardlow, 2024b).

4.3 Evaluating text simplification

Automatic sentence simplification systems are usually evaluated in two ways: (1) automatically, for the similarity of their output to the gold standard manual simplifications; and (2) manually, for grammaticality, simplicity, and meaning preservation of their output sentences. For automatic evaluation, studies commonly use gold standard manually simplified test sentences, and calculate the metrics with scoring algorithms such as BLEU (Papineni et al., 2001) and SARI (Xu et al., 2016). BLEU can be used to compare the simplification produced by a system with a simplification produced by a human; while SARI compares it to the human simplification as well as to the original complex sentence. Automatic evaluation is useful for quickly obtaining rough estimates of performances of different system configurations. Nevertheless, although both scores show some correlations with human assessments, they are not reliable enough for comparing performances

of different simplification systems. Some studies also use the Flesch-Kincaid Readability Index for automatic evaluation (Kincaid et al., 1975). Although well-known in readability research, this metric is not adequate for sentence simplification since it is unsuitable for sentence level simplicity evaluation. Evaluation with final users is rare in text simplification research, although this has been explored in the Simplext project (Saggion et al., 2015), for example, where it was found that, in answering inferential questions in original and simplified versions of a document, no differences were perceived using statistical tests. Qualitative evaluation, however, indicated good reception of a tool able to produce easy-to-read texts. As mentioned above, the easy-to-read method includes final user validation as a key element.

5 Project, tools and demonstrators

Three projects addressing different types of simplification users and languages were PSET (Carroll et al., 1998), for English aphasic readers; PortSimples (Aluísio & Gasperin, 2010), for people with low literacy levels in Brazilian Portuguese; and Simplext (Saggion et al., 2015), for Spanish speakers with intellectual disabilities. While PSET was developed from knowledge of what type of language difficulties aphasic people may face (e.g., passive voice, pronouns), PortSimples and Simplext, although not in the machine learning paradigm, were based on the human study of parallel corpora of original and simplified texts specially developed for the simplification task. These three projects highlight the use of traditional NLP techniques such as parsing and simplification rules to reduce the syntactic complexity of the sentences. The AbleToInclude project created an accessibility layer of simplification in Spanish and English as well as pictogram translation functionalities, which were integrated into several accessibility tools, including an accessible e-mail client (Saggion et al., 2017).

Where wording is a concern, the ClearText project (Espinosa-Zaragoza et al., 2024) proposed the development of a numerical expression simplification system, which implements those rules from the Spanish easy-to-read standard that correspond to the rendering of numerical expressions (dates, times, phone numbers, percentages, ordinals, roman numerals and other quantities). The system is generally rule-based. On the other hand, the project [Easier](#) (Alarcón et al., 2024) offers an interface which implements a complex word identification system enhanced with explanations. The system is based on lexical simplification research: the approach considered a feature-based machine learning approach to classify words into complex or otherwise, and a dictionary-based system to retrieve appropriated synonyms.

For plain language in Spanish, arText and its variant arText Claro (da Cunha, 2022; da Cunha et al., 2017) are examples of applications that seek to linguistically analyse administrative documents, flagging text characteristics which are not compliant with plain language guidelines, and providing recommendations for manual modification. For example, if the text contains nominalisations, the system will highlight these in the text and offer a help box with examples which do comply with the recommendations. Similarly, [Clara](#) is an application to measure the degree of “clarity” of a text. Finally, [Capito](#), a commercial company in Austria, offers an automated tool for translating texts into three different levels (A1, A2, and B1) of the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (Council of Europe, 2020). [CLAPPI](#) translates from Spanish to clear language; according to its creators, the translator was developed by fine-tuning a transformer model.³ For French, [Lisible](#) is a commercial application that assesses the readability of text, offers recommendations powered by ChatGPT to rephrase the text, and suggests synonyms as replacements for complex words. [Hemingway Editor](#) is a web-based and desktop application that assesses the readability

3 No information on fine-tuning or model is provided.

of English texts, offering simplification powered by AI.⁴ ATECA, a Web application developed to assist in the process of identification of documents that do not comply with the easy-to-read normative (Asociación Española de Normalización, 2018), and suggest recommendations to render the text compliant with the current normative (Suárez-Figueroa et al., 2024).

6 Easy-to-read, simplification and social change

Several initiatives from governments and non-profit organisations are contributing to improve access to information for different groups of people. In Spain, as part of its efforts to guarantee maximum accessibility to justice for people with disabilities, the Ministry of Justice has proposed a [plain language writing guide](#) for the judiciary and adapted a set of legal documents to easy-to-read, including minutes, orders, decrees, organisational measures, rulings, sentences and informative notes. The adaptations, designed to serve as annexes to their corresponding original documents, have been configured as templates that can be filled out with the corresponding information in each case (whether an act, order, decree, etc.). Easy-to-read summaries are offered along with the original documents. Moreover, since 2024, the Catalan Government offers a new service for people with disabilities that adapts the content of judicial resolutions such as provisions, orders and sentences to an easy-to-read format.

Easy-to-read information is also relevant in a scientific context: as science is more and more a part of our daily life, it is important that citizens are aware of discoveries, methods and treatments that affect their lives. In this respect, easy-to-read or lay summaries of research papers have been recently investigated in the NLP field at two conferences. On the one hand, the [BioLaySumm 2023](#) conference proposed the development of models to create “abstractive” summaries that are more readable for the general public, containing more background information and less technical terminology (Goldsack et al., 2023). On the other hand, in the context of the CLEF evaluation programme, a task called [SimpleText](#) addresses the use of automated text simplification strategies to improve access to scientific information, including scientific text simplification (Ermakova et al., 2024).

In the democratic arena, it is worthy of note that an estimated 800,000 EU citizens from 16 Member States were not able to participate in the 2019 [European Parliament elections](#) due to barriers such as limited accessibility to polling stations or insufficiently accessible information about candidates and debates. This lack of accessibility to information left a considerable part of the population out of democratic spaces. And even where good initiatives from governments and political parties exist (e.g., provision of political leaflets or information about polling stations in easy-to-read), when it comes to access to democratic and civic participation, no matter how inclusive deliberative and participatory processes and democratic spaces are, people with language difficulties will always be left behind. The language used by policymakers and institutions complicates the involvement of marginalised groups due to language barriers. The objective of the new iDEM project (Saggion et al., 2024), on Innovative and Inclusive Democratic Spaces for Deliberation and Participation, aims to make democratic spaces more accessible for people who experience language difficulties and need provision of easy-to-read formats in order to understand. Applying a user-centered design with a diverse group of people, iDEM will identify ways to linguistically adapt the information utilised in democratic spaces, and develop NLP and AI tools to make information in Catalan, Italian and Spanish more accessible for all.

4 No information on what type of AI is used.

7 Conclusions

Access to information is a fundamental human right which contributes to freedom of expression and self-determination. However, information availability alone is not enough: the way in which information is expressed and presented on paper or in digital format can be extremely complicated to understand and act upon for a highly diverse set of people with varying ranges of reading, writing and understanding abilities. Over the years, several initiatives have emerged (basic English, easy-to-read and plain language) to make information more accessible for all and guidelines, recommendations and norms have emerged. Generally speaking, although these guidelines provide recommendations on layout and linguistic characteristics of easy to understand texts, they are highly subjective and therefore complicated to apply, especially when a translation of existing material into easy-to-read is required.

Artificial intelligence and natural language processing have long dedicated research effort to the development of methods to automate the production of easy-to-read texts. However, and in spite of AI hype, the problem persists. There are several reasons for this: one the one hand, and contrary to the machine translation case, for example, there is insufficient data available to train current AI systems to the performance a human would accept. On the other hand, it is important to keep in mind the user of easy-to-read: no one solution fits all, since different easy-to-read adaptations might be necessary, depending on the target population. Finally, current NLP models such as LLMs are still not well understood and their use in the development of easy-to-read texts needs careful assessment. We know that, if those models generate inaccurate or biased information, this could exacerbate the problem rather than improve access to easy-to-read information.

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9 References

- Alarcón, Rodrigo, Moreno, Lourdes, Martínez, Paloma, & Macías, José A. (2024). EASIER system. Evaluating a Spanish lexical simplification proposal with people with cognitive impairments. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, 40(5), 1195-1209. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10447318.2022.2134074>
- Allen, James. (1995). *Natural language understanding* (2nd edition). Benjamin/Cummings Pub. Co.
- Alonzo, Oliver, Seita, Matthew Glasser, Abraham, & Huenerfauth, Matt. (2020). Automatic text simplification tools for deaf and hard of hearing adults: Benefits of lexical simplification and providing users with autonomy. In Regina Bernhaupt, Florian 'Floyd' Mueller, David Verweij, Josh Andres, Joanna McGrenere, Andy Cockburn, Ignacio Avellino, Alix Goguey, Pernille Bjøn, Shengdong Zhao, Briane Paul Samson & Rafal Kocielnik (Eds.), *CHI '20: CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems, Honolulu, HI, USA, April 25-30, 2020* (pp. 1-13). Association for Computing Machinery. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3313831.3376563>
- Aluísio, Sandra, & Gasperin, Caroline. (2010). Fostering digital inclusion and accessibility: The PorSimples project for simplification of Portuguese texts. In Thamar Solorio & Ted Pedersen (Eds.), *Proceedings of the NAACL HLT 2010 Young Investigators Workshop on Computational Approaches to Languages of the Americas* (pp. 46-53). Association for Computational Linguistics.
- Alva-Manchego, Fernando, Martin, Louise, Bordes, Antoine, Scarton, Carolina, Sagot, Benoît, & Specia, Lucia. (2020). ASSET: A Dataset for Tuning and Evaluation of Sentence Simplification Models with Multiple Rewriting Transformations. In Dan Jurafsky, Joyce Chai, Natalie Schluter & Joel R. Tetreault (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 58th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics* (pp. 4668-4679). Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2020.ACL-MAIN.424>
- Aranzabe, María Jesús, Díaz de Ilarraza, Arantxa, & Gonzalez-Dios, Itziar. (2012). [First approach to automatic text simplification in Basque](#). In Luz Rello & Horacio Saggion (Eds.), *Proceedings of the Natural Language Processing for Improving Textual Accessibility (NLP4ITA) workshop (LREC 2012)* (pp. 1-8). LREC.
- Arch, Andrew. (2009). Web accessibility for older users: Successes and opportunities (keynote). *Proceedings of the 2009 International Cross-Disciplinary Conference on Web Accessibility (W4A)* (pp. 1-6). Association for Computing Machinery. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1535654.1535655>
- Arenas Arias, Germán J. (2023). Publish, explain, understand, and comply: Legislation in plain language. *The Theory and Practice of Legislation*, 11(2), 107-135. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20508840.2023.2182980>
- Asociación Española de Normalización. (2018). *UNE 153101:2018 EX: Lectura Fácil. Pautas y recomendaciones para la elaboración de documentos*.
- Barthe, Kathy, Juaneda, Claire, Leseigneur, Dominique, Loquet, Jean-Claude, Morin, Claude, Escande, Jean, & Vayrette, Annick. (1999). GIFAS rationalized French: A controlled language for aerospace documentation in French. *Technical Communication*, 46(2), 220-229.
- Beard, John R., Officer, Alana, Araujo de Carvalho, Islene, Sadana, Ritu, Pot, Anne Margriet, Michel, Jean-Pierre, Lloyd-Sherlock, Peter, Epping-Jordan, JoAnne E., Peeters, G. M. E. E. (Geeske), Mahanani, Wahyu Retnu, Thiyagarajan, Jotheeswaran Amuthavalli, & Chatterji, Somnath. (2016). The world report on ageing and health: A policy framework for healthy ageing. *The Lancet*, 387(10033), 2145-2154. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(15\)00516-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(15)00516-4)
- Biran, Or, Brody, Samuel, & Elhadad, Noémie. (2011). Putting it simply: A context-aware approach to lexical simplification. In Dekang Lin, Yuji Matsumoto & Rada Mihalcea (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 49th Annual*

- Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies* (pp. 496-501). Association for Computational Linguistics.
- Bott, Stefan, Rello, Luz, Drndarević, Biljana, & Saggion, Horacio. (2012). Can Spanish be simpler? LexSiS: Lexical Simplification for Spanish. In Martin Kay & Christian Boitet (Eds.), *Proceedings of COLING 2012* (pp. 357-374). COLING 2012 Organizing Committee.
- Bott, Stefan, & Saggion, Horacio. (2011). Spanish text simplification: An exploratory study. *Procesamiento del Lenguaje Natural*, 47(0), 87-95.
- Brown, Kristine. (1995). Current issues in plain English. *ARIS Bulletin*, 6(4).
- Carroll, John, Minnen, Guido, Canning, Yvonne, Devlin, Siobhan, & Tait, John. (1998). Practical simplification of English newspaper text to assist aphasic readers. *Proceedings of AAAI-98 Workshop on Integrating Artificial Intelligence and Assistive Technology*, 7-10.
- Chandrasekar, Raman, Doran, Christine, & Bangalore, Srinivas. (1996). Motivations and Methods for Text Simplification. *COLING 1996 Volume 2: The 16th International Conference on Computational Linguistics* (pp. 1041-1044).
- Collobert, Ronan, Weston, Jason, Bottou, Léon, Karlen, Michael, Kavukcuoglu, Koray, & Kuksa, Pavel. (2011). Natural Language Processing (Almost) from Scratch. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 12, 2493-2537.
- Council of Europe. (2020). *Common European framework of reference for languages: Learning, teaching, assessment – Companion volume*. Council of Europe Publishing.
- Crystal, David. (1987). *The Cambridge encyclopedia of language* (1st edition). Cambridge University Press.
- Da Cunha, Iria. (2022). Un redactor asistido para adaptar textos administrativos a lenguaje claro. *Procesamiento del Lenguaje Natural*, 69, 39-49.
- Da Cunha, Iria, Montané March, Maria Amor, & Hysa, Luis. (2017). The arText prototype: An automatic system for writing specialized texts. In André Martins & Anselmo Peñas (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 15th Conference of the European Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics* (pp. 57-60). Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://doi.org/10.18653/V1/E17-3015>
- De Belder, Jan, & Moens, Marie-Francine. (2012). A dataset for the evaluation of lexical simplification. In Alexander Gelbukh (Ed.), *Computational Linguistics and Intelligent Text Processing* (pp. 426-437). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- Devlin, Jacob, Chang, Ming-Wei, Lee, Kenton, & Toutanova, Kristina. (2019). BERT: Pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers for language understanding. In Jill Burstein, Christy Doran & Tamar Solorio (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 2019 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies, Volume 1 (Long and Short Papers)* (pp. 4171-4186). Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://doi.org/10.18653/V1/N19-1423>
- Ermakova, Liana, SanJuan, Eric, Huet, Stéphane, Azarbondy, Hosein, Di Nunzio, Georgio Maria, Vezzani, Frederika, D'Souza, Jennifer, Kabongo Kabenamualu, Salomon, Giglou, Hamed Babaei, Zhang, Yue, Auer, Sören, & Kamps, Jaap. (2024). CLEF 2024 SimpleText Track—Improving access to scientific texts for everyone. In Nazli Goharian, Nicola Tonello, Yulan He, Aldo Lipani, Graham McDonald, Craig Macdonald & Iadh Ounis (Eds.), *Advances in Information Retrieval—46th European Conference on Information Retrieval, ECIR 2024, Glasgow, UK, March 24-28, 2024, Proceedings, Part IV* (pp. 28-35). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-56072-9_4

- Espinosa-Zaragoza, Isabel, Moreda, Paloma, & Palomar, Manuel. (2024). Enhancing clarity: An evaluation of the Simple.Text tool for numerical expression simplification. *Procesamiento del Lenguaje Natural*, 72, 99-108.
- Fajardo, Inmaculada, Ávila, Vicenta, Ferrer, Antonio, Tavares, Gema, Gómez, Marcos, & Hernández, Ana. (2014). Easy-to-read texts for students with intellectual disability: Linguistic factors affecting comprehension. *Journal of Applied Research in Intellectual Disabilities: JARID*, 27(3), 212-225. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jar.12065>
- Ferrés, Daniel, & Saggion, Horacio. (2022). [ALEXISIS: A dataset for lexical simplification in Spanish](#). In Nicoletta Calzolari, Frederic Bechet, Philippe Blache, Khalid Choukri, Christopher Cieri, Thierry Declerck, Sara Goggi, Hitoshi Isahara, Bente Maegaard, Joseph Mariani, Helene Mazo, Jan Odijk & Stelios Piperidis (Eds.), *Proceedings of the Thirteenth Language Resources and Evaluation Conference* (pp. 3582-3594). European Language Resources Association.
- Gallardo, Ana, García, Óscar, Pindado, Beatriz, Sánchez, Carlos, Mifsut, Carmen María, Luján, Eva, Cano, Isabel, Pineda, Jacob, Palazuelos, María Adela, Ansiporovich, Jonathan, Fernández, José Manuel, Bernal, Manuel, Uría, Neisy, Hernández, Ruth, & Gallego, Susana. (2018). *Validación de textos en lectura fácil: Aspectos prácticos y sociolaborales*. Plena Inclusión Madrid.
- García, Óscar. (2012). [Lectura fácil: Métodos de redacción y evaluación](#). Real Patronato sobre Discapacidad.
- Gasparin, Caroline, Specia, Lucía, Pereira, Tiago F., & Aluisio, Sandra María. (2009). Learning when to simplify sentences for natural text simplification. *Encontro Nacional de Inteligência Artificial*, 809-818.
- Glavaš, Goran, & Štajner, Sanja. (2015). Simplifying lexical simplification: Do we need simplified corpora? In Chengqing Zong & Michael Strube (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 53rd Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics and the 7th International Joint Conference on Natural Language Processing (Volume 2: Short Papers)* (pp. 63-68).
- Goldsack, Tomas, Luo, Zheheng, Xie, Qianqian, Scarton, Carolina, Shardlow, Matthew, Ananiadou, Sophia, & Lin, Chenghua. (2023). Overview of the BioLaySumm 2023 shared task on lay summarization of biomedical research articles. In Dina Demner-fushman, Sophia Ananiadou & Kevin Cohen (Eds.), *The 22nd Workshop on Biomedical Natural Language Processing and BioNLP Shared Tasks* (pp. 468-477). Association for Computational Linguistics.
- Gonzalez-Dios, Itziar, Aranzabe, María Jesús, & Díaz de Ilarraza, Arantza. (2018). The corpus of Basque simplified texts (CBST). *Language Resources and Evaluation*, 52(1), 217-247. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10579-017-9407-6>
- González-Sordé, Mariona, & Matamala, Anna. (2024). Empirical evaluation of easy language recommendations: A systematic literature review from journal research in Catalan, English, and Spanish. *Universal Access in the Information Society*, 23(3), 1369-1387. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10209-023-00975-2>
- Hmida, Firas, Billami, Mokhtar B., François, Thomas, & Gala, Núria. (2018). Assisted lexical simplification for French native children with reading difficulties. In Arne Jönsson, Evelina Rennes, Horacio Saggion, Sanja Stajner & Victoria Yaneva (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 1st Workshop on Automatic Text Adaptation (ATA)* (pp. 21-28). Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/W18-7004>
- Horn, Colby, Manduca, Cathryn, & Kauchak, David. (2014). Learning a lexical simplifier using Wikipedia. In Kristina Toutanova & Hua Wu (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 52nd Annual Meeting of the Association*

- for Computational Linguistics (Volume 2: Short Papers)* (pp. 458-463). Association for Computational Linguistics.
- International Organization for Migration. (2019). *DTM Europe—Mixed migration flows to Europe, Quarterly Overview*.
- International Organization for Standardization. (2023). *ISO/IEC 23859:2023: Information technology—User interfaces—Requirements and recommendations on making written text easy to read and understand*.
- Kajiwar, Tomoyuki, & Yamamoto, Kazuhide. (2015). Evaluation dataset and system for Japanese lexical simplification. In Kuan-Yu Chen, Angelina Ivanova, Ellie Pavlick, Emily Bender, Chin-Yew Lin & Stephan Oepen (Eds.), *Proceedings of the ACL-IJCNLP 2015 Student Research Workshop* (pp. 35-40). Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://doi.org/10.3115/v1/P15-3006>
- Kincaid, J. Peter, Fishburne Jr., Robert P., Rogers, Richard L., & Chissom, Brad S. (1975). Derivation of new readability formulas (automated readability index, fog count and Flesch reading ease formula) for Navy enlisted personnel. *Institute for Simulation and Training*, 56. Institute for Simulation and Training, University of Central Florida.
- Lewis, Michael, Liu, Yinhan, Goyal, Naman, Ghazvininejad, Marjan, Mohamed, Abdelrahman, Levy, Omer, Stoyanov, Veselin, & Zettlemoyer, Luke. (2020). BART: Denoising sequence-to-sequence Pre-training for natural language generation, translation, and comprehension. In Dan Jurafsky, Joyce Chai, Natalie Schluter & Joel Tetreault (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 58th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics* (pp. 7871-7880). Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2020.ACL-MAIN.703>
- Maaß, Christiane. (2020). *Easy language - plain language - easy language plus: Balancing comprehensibility and acceptability*. Frank & Timme, Verlag für wissenschaftliche Literatur.
- Manning, Christopher D., & Schütze, Hinrich. (2000). *Foundations of statistical natural language processing* (2nd edition with corrections). MIT Press.
- Martin, Louis, de la Clergerie, Éric, Sagot, Benoît, & Bordes, Antione. (2020). [Controllable Sentence Simplification](#). In Nicoletta Calzolari, Frédéric Béchet, Philippe Blache, Khalid Choukri, Christopher Cieri, Thierry Declerck, Sara Goggi, Hitoshi Isahara, Bente Maegaard, Joseph Mariani, Hélène Mazo, Asuncion Moreno, Jan Odijk & Stelios Piperidis (Eds.), *Proceedings of the Twelfth Language Resources and Evaluation Conference, LREC 2020, Marseille, France, May 11-16, 2020* (pp. 4689-4698). European Language Resources Association.
- Matamala, Anna. (2022). Easy-to-understand language in audiovisual translation and accessibility: State of the art and future challenges. *XLinguae*, 15(2), 130-144. <https://doi.org/10.18355/XL.2022.15.02.10>
- Mikolov, Tomas, Yih, Wen-Tau, & Zweig, Geoffrey. (2013). Linguistic regularities in continuous space word representations. In Lucy Vanderwende, Hal Daumé III & Katrin Kirchhoff (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 2013 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association of Computational Linguistics* (pp. 746-751). Association for Computational Linguistics.
- Miller, George A., Beckwith, Richard, Fellbaum, Christiane, Gross, Derek, & Miller, Katherine J. (1990). Introduction to WordNet: An on-line lexical database. *International Journal of Lexicography*, 3(4), 235-244.
- Mitkov, Ruslan (Ed.). (2021). *The Oxford handbook of computational linguistics* (2nd edition). Oxford University Press.

- Mitkov, Ruslan, & Štajner, Sanja. (2014). The fewer, the better? A contrastive study about ways to simplify. In Constantin Orasan, Petya Osenova & Cristina Vertan (Eds.), *Proceedings of the Workshop on Automatic Text Simplification—Methods and Applications in the Multilingual Society (ATS-MA 2014)* (pp. 30-40). Association for Computational Linguistics and Dublin City University. <https://doi.org/10.3115/v1/W14-5604>
- Murman, Daniel L. (2015). The impact of age on cognition. *Seminars in Hearing*, 36(03), 111-121. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0035-1555115>
- Navigli, Roberto, & Ponzetto, Simone Paolo. (2010). [BabelNet: Building a very large multilingual semantic network](#). In Jan Hajič, Sandra Carberry, Stephen Clark & Joakim Nivre (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 48th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics* (pp. 216-225). Association for Computational Linguistics.
- Nisioi, Sergiu, Stajner, Sanja, Ponzetto, Simone Paolo, & Dinu, Liviu P. (2017). Exploring neural text simplification models. In Regina Barzilay & Min-Yen Kan (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 55th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (Volume 2: Short Papers)* (pp. 85-91). Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://doi.org/10.18653/V1/P17-2014>
- Nomura, Misako, Tronbacke, Bror, & Skat Nielsen, Gyda. (2010). *Guidelines for easy-to-read materials* (IFLA Professional Reports, No. 120). International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions.
- North, Kai, Zampieri, Marcos, & Shardlow, Matthew. (2023). Lexical complexity prediction: An overview. *ACM Computing Surveys*, 55(9), 179:1-179:42. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3557885>
- Ogden, Charles Kay. (1932). *Basic English: A general introduction with rules and grammar*. K. Paul, Trench, Trubner & Co., Ltd.
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. (2013). *OECD skills outlook 2013: First results from the survey of adult skills*. OECD. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264204256-en>
- Papineni, Kishore, Roukos, Salim, Ward, Todd, & Zhu, Wei-Jing. (2001). BLEU: A method for automatic evaluation of machine translation. In Pierre Isabelle, Eugene Charniak & Dekang Lin (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 40th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics* (pp. 311-318). Association for Computational Linguistics.
- Qiang, Jipeng, Li, Yun, Zhu, Yi, Yuan, Yunhau, & Wu, Xindong. (2020). Lexical simplification with pretrained encoders. *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, 34(05), 8649-8656. <https://doi.org/10.1609/aaai.v34i05.6389>
- Qiang, Jipeng, Lu, Xinyu, Li, Yun, Yuan, Yunhau, & Wu, Xindong. (2021). Chinese lexical simplification. *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing*, 29, 1819-1828. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TASLP.2021.3078361>
- Raffel, Colin, Shazeer, Noam, Roberts, Adam, Lee, Katherine, Narang, Sharan, Matena, Michael, Zhou, Yanqi, Li, Wei, & Liu, Peter J. (2020). Exploring the limits of transfer learning with a unified text-to-text transformer. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 21, 140:1-140:67.
- Reiter, Ehud, & Dale, Robert. (2006). *Building natural language generation systems*. Cambridge University Press.
- Rello, Luz, Baeza-Yates, Ricardo A., Bott, Stefan, & Saggion, Horacio. (2013). Simplify or help?: Text simplification strategies for people with dyslexia. In Giorgio Brajnik & Paola Salomoni (Eds.), *W4A '13: Proceedings of the 10th International Cross-Disciplinary Conference on Web Accessibility* (pp. 15:1-15:10). Association for Computing Machinery.

- Russell, Stuart, & Norvig, Peter. (2010). *Artificial intelligence: A modern approach* (3rd edition). Prentice Hall.
- Saggion, Horacio, Ferrés, Daniel, Sevens, Leen, Schuurman, Inecke, Ripollés, Marta, & Rodríguez, Olga. (2017). Able to read my mail: An accessible e-mail client with assistive technology. *W4A'17: Proceedings of the 14th International Web for All Conference* (pp. 5:1-5:4). Association for Computing Machinery.
- Saggion, Horacio, O'Flaherty, John, Blanchet, Thomas, Sharoff, Serge, Sanfilippo, Silvia, Muñoz, Lian, Gollegger, Martin, Rascón, Almudena, Martí, José Luis, Szasz, Sandra, Bott, Stefan Markus, & Sayman, Volkan. (2024). Making democratic deliberation and participation more accessible: The iDEM project. In Alba Bonet-Jover, Robiert Sepúlveda-Torres, Rafael Muñoz Guillena, Eugenio Martínez-Cámara, Elena Lloret Pastor, Álvaro Rodrigo-Yuste & Aitziber Atutxa (Eds.), *Proceedings of the Seminar of the Spanish Society for Natural Language Processing: Projects and System Demonstrations (SEPLN-CEDI-PD 2024) co-located with the 7th Spanish Conference on Informatics* (pp. 71-76). CEUR Workshop Proceedings.
- Saggion, Horacio, Štajner, Sanja, Bott, Stefan, Mille, Simon, Rello, Luz, & Drndarević, Biljana. (2015). Making it Simplex: Implementation and evaluation of a text simplification system for Spanish. *ACM Transactions on Accessible Computing (TACCESS)*, 6(4), 14.
- Saggion, Horacio, Štajner, Sanja, Ferrés, Daniel, Sheang, Kim Cheng, Shardlow, Matthew, North, Kai, & Zampieri, Marcos. (2022). Findings of the TSAR-2022 shared task on multilingual lexical simplification. In Sanja Štajner, Horacio Saggion, Daniel Ferrés, Matthew Shardlow, Kim Cheng Sheang, Kai North, Marcos Zampieri & Wei Xu (Eds.), *Proceedings of the Workshop on Text Simplification, Accessibility, and Readability (TSAR-2022)* (pp. 271-283). Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2022.tsar-1.31>
- Sauvan, Lauren, Stolowy, Natacha, Aguilar, Carlos, François, Thomas, Gala, Núria, Matonti, Frédéric, Castet, Eric, & Calabrèse, Aurélie. (2020). Text simplification to help individuals with low vision read more fluently. In Núria Gala & Rodrigo Wilkens (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 1st Workshop on Tools and Resources to Empower People with READING Difficulties (READI)* (pp. 27-32). European Language Resources Association. <https://www.aclweb.org/anthology/2020.readi-1.5/>
- Scarton, Carolina, & Specia, Lucia. (2018). Learning simplifications for specific target audiences. In Iryna Gurevych & Yusuke Miyao (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 56th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics, ACL 2018, Melbourne, Australia, July 15-20, 2018, Volume 2: Short Papers* (pp. 712-718). Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://doi.org/10.18653/V1/P18-2113>
- Shardlow, Matthew, Alva-Manchego, Fernando, Batista-Navarro, Riza, Bott, Stefan, Calderon Ramirez, Saul, Cardon, Rémi, François, Thomas, Hayakawa, Akio, Horbach, Andrea, Hülsing, Anna, Ide, Yusuke, Imperial, Joseph Marvin, Nohejl, Adam, North, Kai, Occhipinti, Laura, Pérez Rojas, Nelson, Raihan, Nishat, Ranasinghe, Tharindu, Solis Salazar, Martin, Zampieri, Marcos, & Saggion, Horacio. (2024). An extensible massively multilingual lexical simplification pipeline dataset using the MultiLS framework. In Rodrigo Wilkens, Rémi Cardon, Amalia Todirascu & Núria Gala (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 3rd Workshop on Tools and Resources for People with READING Difficulties (READI) @ LREC-COLING 2024* (pp. 38-46). ELRA and ICCL.
- Shardlow, Matthew, Alva-Manchego, Fernando, Batista-Navarro, Riza, Bott, Stefan, Calderon Ramirez, Saul, Cardon, Rémi, François, Thomas, Hayakawa, Akio, Horbach, Andrea, Hülsing, Anna., Ide, Yusuke, Imperial, Joseph Marvin, Nohejl, Adam, North, Kai, Occhipinti, Laura, Rojas, Nelson Pérez, Raihan, Nishat, Ranasinghe, Tharindu, Salazar, Martin Solis, Štajner, Sanja, Zampieri, Marcos, & Saggion, Horacio. (2024). [The BEA 2024 Shared task on the multilingual lexical simplification pipeline](#). In Ekaterina Kochmar, Marie Bexte, Jill Burstein, Andrea Horbach, Ronja Laarmann-Quante, Anaïs Tack, Victoria Yaneva & Zheng Yuan (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 19th Workshop on Innovative Use of NLP for Building Educational Applications (BEA 2024)* (pp. 571-589). Association for Computational Linguistics.

- Sheang, Kim Cheng, & Saggion, Horacio. (2021). Controllable sentence simplification with a unified text-to-text transfer transformer. In Anya Belz, Angela Fan, Ehud Reiter & Yaji Sripada (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 14th International Conference on Natural Language Generation* (pp. 341-352). Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://doi.org/10.18653/V1/2021.INLG-1.38>
- Specia, Lucia. (2010). [Translating from complex to simplified sentences](#). In Thiago Alexandre Salgueiro Pardo, António Branco, Aldebaro Klautau, Renata Vieira & Vera Lúcia Strube Lima (Eds.), *Computational Processing of the Portuguese Language* (pp. 30-39). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- Specia, Lucia, Jauhar, Sujay Kumar, & Mihalcea, Rada. (2012). SemEval-2012 task 1: English lexical simplification. In Eneko Agirre, Johan Bos, Mona Diab, Suresh Manandhar, Yuval Marton & Deniz Yuret (Eds.), **SEM 2012: The First Joint Conference on Lexical and Computational Semantics – Volume 1: Proceedings of the main conference and the shared task, and Volume 2: Proceedings of the Sixth International Workshop on Semantic Evaluation (SemEval 2012)* (pp. 347-355). Association for Computational Linguistics.
- Štajner, Sanja, & Saggion, Horacio. (2015). [Translating from original to simplified sentences using Moses: When does it actually work?](#). In Ruslan Mitkov, Galia Angelova & Kalina Bontcheva (Eds.), *Proceedings of the International Conference Recent Advances in Natural Language Processing* (pp. 611-617). INCOMA Ltd. Shoumen.
- Štajner, Sanjar, Sheang, Kim Cheng, & Saggion, Horacio. (2022). Sentence simplification capabilities of transfer-based models. *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, 36(11), 12172-12180. <https://doi.org/10.1609/AAAI.V36I11.21477>
- Suárez-Figueroa, Mari Carmen, Diab, Isam, Ruckhaus, Edna, & Cano, Isabel. (2024). First steps in the development of a support application for easy-to-read adaptation. *Universal Access in the Information Society*, 23(1), 365-377.
- Šveřepa, Milan. (2021). [Information for all: European standards for making information easy to read and understand](#). Inclusion Europe.
- Tonelli, Sara, Aprosio, Alessio Palmero, & Saltori, Francesca (2016). SIMPITIKI: a Simplification corpus for Italian. In Pierpaolo Basile, Anna Corazza, Franco Cutugno, Simonetta Montemagni, Malvina Nissim, Viviana Patti, Giovanni Semeraro & Rachele Sprugnoli (Eds.), *Proceedings of the Third Italian Conference on Computational Linguistics (CLiC-it 2016)* (pp. 291-296). CEUR Workshop Proceedings.
- UNESCO Institute for Statistics. (2017). *Literacy rates continue to rise from one generation to the next* [Fact sheet No. 45].
- UNESCO Institute for Statistics. (2018). *Education and disability: Analysis of data from 49 countries* [Information sheet No.49].
- Vaswani, Ashish, Shazeer, Noam, Parmar, Niki, Uszkoreit, Jakob, Jones, Llion, Gomez, Aidan N., Kaiser, Lukasz, & Polosukhin, Illia. (2017). [Attention is all you need](#). In Isabelle Guyon, Ulrike von Luxburg, Samy Bengio, Hanna M. Wallach, Rob Fergus, S. V. N. Vishwanathan & Roman Garnett (Eds.), *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 30 (NIPS 2017)* (pp. 5998-6008). NeurIPS Proceedings.
- Woodsend, Kristian, & Lapata, Mirella. (2011). Learning to simplify sentences with quasi-synchronous grammar and integer programming. In Regina Barzilay & Mark Johnson (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 2011 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing* (pp. 409-420). Association for Computational Linguistics.

- Wubben, Sander, van den Bosch, Antal, & Krahmer, Emiel. (2012). Sentence simplification by monolingual machine translation. In Haizhou Li, Chin-Yew Lin, Miles Osborne, Gary Geunbae Lee & Jong C. Park (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 50th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (Volume 1: Long Papers)* (pp. 1015-1024). Association for Computational Linguistics.
- Xu, Wei, Callison-Burch, Chris, & Napoles, Courtney. (2015). Problems in current text simplification research: New data can help. *Transactions of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, 3, 283-297.
- Xu, Wei, Napoles, Courtney, Pavlick, Ellie, Chen, Quanze, & Callison-Burch, Chris. (2016). Optimizing statistical machine translation for text simplification. *Transactions of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, 4, 401-415.
- Zampieri, Marcos, Malmasi, Shervin, Paetzold, Gustavo, & Specia, Lucia. (2017). [Complex word identification: Challenges in data annotation and system performance](#). In Yuen-Hsien Tseng, Hsin-Hsi Chen, Lung-Hao Lee & Liang-Chih Yu (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 4th Workshop on Natural Language Processing Techniques for Educational Applications (NLPTEA 2017)* (pp. 59-63). Asian Federation of Natural Language Processing.
- Zhang, Xingxing, & Lapata, Mirella. (2017). Sentence simplification with deep reinforcement learning. In Martha Palmer, Rebecca Hwa & Sebastian Riedel (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 2017 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing* (pp. 584-594). Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://doi.org/10.18653/V1/D17-1062>